

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE INITIAL RESULTS OF THE STATUS OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT AND MOTOR TRAINING FOR PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS FROM URBAN LOCATIONS OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

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Abstract

The present article addresses the problem of recovering the children scoliosis by means of complex treatment, including active correction through physical exercises and massage.

Keywords: flat feet, scoliosis, obesity, evaluation methods, motor tests, recovery, massage.

Actuality. The research on the development of the growing generations, children and adolescents, occupies an important place among international and national studies. Our study reflects an important side of physical and motor development and the occurrence of some conditions at primary school students. The analysis of the physical and motor condition of primary school students from the urban areas of the Republic of Moldova demonstrates the fact that their development took place in accordance with the normal physiological processes in the human body, which adequately reflect the particularities of the natural and social environment in which people live and work evaluated.

The purpose of the research. Prevention of attitude deficiencies and more serious conditions should start at school age, and this is possible through school screening. Detecting these deviations in time and treating them during childhood must be a major objective for our society. Children with deficient attitudes should be under continuous supervision.

Methods. In order to achieve this goal, the author organized their research using various methods, as follows: theoretical analysis and generalization of specialized literature data; anthropometric assessment method; somatoscopic evaluation method; the pedagogical observation method; the plantographic method; Quetelet method, motor tests.

Results. Table 1 shows the data of the anthropometric study on primary school children in urban schools, located in different geographical regions of the country: north; center and south [5].

The results of the research of the physical condition of children in primary classes, according to the anthropometric indicators of height, weight and rib cage excursion, demonstrate the fact that in all regions of the country, both boys and girls developed normally, according to the physiological age characteristics. At the

same time, the normality indicators of the Quetelet index, which characterize the optimal ratios between weight and height, indicate that the most favorable environment for the development of boys was in the cities from the north of the country. Lower values were recorded in schools from the cities located in the center (93.34%) and in the south of the country (92.50%). This is also confirmed by the comparative statistical analysis of the physical development indicators of the boys in the primary classes. At the same time, no significant difference was observed in the height indicators of the boys from the three urban regions ($P > 0.05$). At the same time, a true difference was observed between the boys from the cities in the center of the country and those from the cities in the north in terms of the weight indicators ($P < 0.01$). This difference indicates that most of the investigated boys from the center of the country dominate to a greater extent according to the Quetelet index, at a coefficient of 0.21, with a little excess weight. Unlike the group of boys from the central area, the boys from the north, having the same ratios between weight and height, were placed within the limits of normality (up to 0.30).

The same evaluation related to girls in the primary cycle demonstrated the fact that in the cities of the South and the North, girls grow up approximately at the same time and, respectively, the results of the research of these cities have an invalid character of relative difference ($P > 0.05$). At the same time, primary school girls from Northern and Southern cities grow somewhat faster compared to primary school girls from Central cities ($P < 0.01-0.001$). The same situation can be observed in the case of studying the weight indicators of primary school girls in the investigated schools and cities. Of particular importance are the indicators of the Quetelet index that characterize the ratios between weight and height, and which were within the normal range (from 0.20 to 0.30).

Table 1.

The statistical characteristics of the results of the anthropometric assessment of children in the primary classes of educational institutions from the urban environment of the Republic of Moldova

City	Tests							
	Girls				Boys			
	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	Rib cage excursion (cm)	Quetelet index (%)	Height (cm)	Weight (kg)	Rib cage excursion (cm)	Quetelet index (%)
Center	129,54± 1,08	26,71± 0,33	5,20±0,43	100%	133,34± 0,99	32,76± 0,63	5,60± 0,34	93,34%
North	135,37± 1,42	29,80± 1,02	5,33±0,43	100%	133,56± 0,58	29,37± 0,95	5,13± 0,23	100%
South	136,43± 1,44	30,97± 1,00	5,05±0,46	100%	135,41± 1,52	29,84±1,39	4,40± 0,29	92,50%
\bar{X}	133,78± 1,31	29,16± 0,78	5,19±0,44	100%	134,11± 1,03	30,66±0,99	5,04± 0,28	95,28%

Studying the indicators of the rib cage excursion at primary school girls from the mentioned cities, we can observe a relatively uniform regional development of them ($P>0.05$). At the same time, was observed a true difference ($P<0.01$) between boys from primary urban schools, especially boys from the central cities compared to those from the south of the country, which apparently indicates the great possibilities of the body's cardiorespiratory system children from the cities in the center of the country.

The results presented in table 2 about the motor condition of the examined students, characterize the degree of development of the abilities of strength, strength-speed, coordination of movements and flexibility of the trunk of children in primary classes. These statistical data reflect a balance in the development of the growing generation with certain relative differences, from a regional point of view where $P>0.05$.

The only exceptions are the indicators of the test "leaning forward from the gymnastic bench, hands down", which indicate a true difference of them, where ($P<0.01$). between the results evaluated at the boys from the central cities compared to those from the south and the north of the country in favor of children from the center of the country. The comparative analysis between the results evaluated for boys from the cities in the center, south, and north of the country indicate a difference in favor of children from the center of the country.

At the same time, the comparative analysis of the locomotor condition of primary school girls from the north, center and south cities indicates untrue differences ($P>0.05$) at the results of most tests, i.e. the development of strength, strength-speed and trunk flexibility of these girls occurs approximately the same in all schools of the mentioned cities.

Table 2.

The results of the investigation of the motor development of primary school students from educational institutions in the Republic of Moldova.

City	Tests							
	Girls				Boys			
	Running-suveica (sec)	Standing long jump (cm)	Raising the trunk from the lying position in 30 sec. (no. of repeats)	Forward bend on the gym bench (cm)	Running-suveica (sec)	Standing long jump (cm)	Raising the trunk from the lying position in 30 sec. (no. of repeats)	Forward bend on the gym bench (cm)
Center	9,69± 0,05	134,31± 2,70	17,88± 0,75	7,45± 0,95	9,29± 0,11	140,60± 5,35	18,35± 0,85	6,08± 0,69
North	8,92± 0,12	124,36± 2,35	19,42± 0,68	7,47± 1,11	9,00± 0,21	136,06± 3,55	18,83± 0,52	3,28± 0,95
South	8,94± 0,11	128,53± 2,39	19,40± 0,83	6,69± 1,03	9,55± 0,26	135,83± 3,79	18,53± 0,66	4,04± 1,11
\bar{X}	9,18± 0,09	129,07± 2,48	18,90± 0,75	7,20± 1,03	9,28± 0,19	137,50± 4,23	18,57± 0,68	4,47± 0,84

The only exceptions are the results of the sprint and long jump tests, which mainly reflect strength and coordination skills, as well as a certain side of strength-speed skills. These results demonstrate the fact that girls from cities in the north and south develop relatively the same ($P>0.05$), while, in comparison with girls from urban areas in the center, true differences are observed ($P<0.01-0.001$) in favor of primary school girls from the north and south. This situation can probably be explained by a best physical education instructional process, organized for primary school children from the center of the country, contributed to a greater extent to the development of their trunk flexibility, in the presence of other similar conditions [1, 2].

In the same way, evaluating the obtained results, was also found some deviations from the normal development of the children included in the study. The indicators of the basic negative factors of physical develop-

ment, which reflect the presence in primary school children of conditions such as flat feet, scoliosis and obesity.

The foot was evaluated using the plantogram method. In this context, the first place after the presence of flat feet in primary school boys is occupied by the schools in the south of the country (33.33%), the second place - the schools in the center (28.33%), and the third place - the schools in the north of the country (23.33%) [3, 5].

Studying the existence of some negative factors of physical development in primary school girls from the investigated cities was ascertained that flat feet prevails considerably over scoliosis and obesity. Thus, the largest number of girls with flat feet were diagnosed in northern cities (44.44%), followed by those in the south (36.66%), and fewer cases were confirmed in the center (28.33 %).

Table 3.

The existence of negative factors of the physical development of primary school students in urban educational institutions in the Republic of Moldova

No. crt.	Negative factors of physical development	Center	North	South	Average index	Distribution of places according to negative factors		
						I	II	III
1	Platypodia %	28,33	23,33	33,33	28,33	South	Center	North
2	Scoliosis %	3,33	5,00	15,00	7,78	South	North	Center
3	Obesity %	6,66	—	7,50	7,08	South	Center	—

In the research process, the somatoscopic evaluation of the spine was emphasized, in order to verify or exclude some postural changes of the students included in the study. In this context, the presence of scoliosis at primary school boys is higher in the city from the south (15%), followed by those from the north (5.00%), and the fewest cases were in the center (3.33%). At the same time, the presence of scoliosis in an early stage at primary school girls is much lower compared to the presence of flat feet. In this context, 6.66% of cases were registered in the center, 5.00% in the north, and 10.00% of cases were observed in the south, which occupies the first position after this disease.

Another important indicator evaluated by us in this study was body mass. The evaluation method selected is the Quetelet index. Regarding primary obesity indices, the first place is occupied by primary school boys from the southern town, where, has been observed children with increased weight characteristics in relation to height (7.50%). In the schools of in the center, a much smaller number of boys in primary classes suffering from excess weight - (6.66%). At the same time, the most favorable situation from the point of view of obesity among primary school boys was observed in schools in the north, where no overweight boy was detected among the examined children.

This fact is also demonstrated by the characteristics of weight and height (according to the Quetelet index) observed in primary school boys from the schools of North. An important moment in this study is represented by the fact that primary school girls from all the mentioned cities practically do not show significant deviations regarding the indicators of the initial stage of obesity. Apparently, this phenomenon can be explained

by the fact that girls of this age have an intense locomotor activity, associated with their domestic characteristics that distinguish them from their male peers. It should also be noted that flat feet is the most pronounced negative condition recorded in primary school boys and girls.

Thus, it should be mentioned that in most cases, the physical condition of primary school students from all regions of the Republic of Moldova corresponds to the age-specific physiological characteristics of their organism's development in relation to the conditioned social environment.

In most cases, no true differences were observed in the locomotor condition of primary school boys from the three different geographical regions (Center, North, South). At the same time, negative factors (flat feet, scoliosis, obesity) were detected in primary school boys from all three mentioned regions. These factors are more intensive in the southern cities (from 10 % to 33.33%) and to a lesser extent in the northern cities (from 5.00% to 23.33%). Also in this context, it can be emphasized that among the boys of the primary classes in the town of the North, a better situation was observed in the case of flat foot deficiencies (23.33%) and scoliosis (5.00%). At boys from primary schools of the central cities suffer of obesity 6.66%, and at those from the southern cities -10%. At the same time, the primary school boys from the northern towns have a best situation from the point of view of primary obesity. Thus, in the northern primary schools, no overweight boy was detected among all the children examined. The obtained results are also confirmed by the characteristics of weight and height (according to the Quetelet index) observed at primary school boys from the northern schools.

The analysis of the existence of negative factors among primary school people from the three different geographical regions (Center, North, South) demonstrates that in the south prevails such factors in relation to the north and center. Among these negative factors, scoliosis predominates, which affects up to 33.33% of children. In our opinion, this situation is conditioned by the fact that in the southern cities, there is a more precarious situation in terms of the unfavorable sanitary-hygienic conditions for the development of children of the given age. At the same time, the given situation is influenced to a lesser extent by some family conditions (including parental hereditary factors) and to a greater extent by the disadvantaged sanitary-hygienic conditions in the school.

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